

Detection of Underground cable fault using Arduino and GSM module

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Abstract- The main objective of this project is to detect the faults and abnormalities occurring in underground cables using an arduino. The basic idea behind the working of this project is ohms law .At the feeder end, when a DC voltage is applied, based on the location of fault in the cable, the value of current also changes. So in case of a short circuit fault like L-G or L-L fault the change in voltage value measured across the resistor is then fed to the in-built ADC of the arduino. This value is processed by the arduino and the fault is calculated in terms of distance from the base station .This value is sent to the LCD interfaced to the arduino board and it displays exact location of the fault from the base station in kilometers for all the three phases. This project is arranged with a set of resistors which represent the length of the cable. At every known kilometer fault switches are placed to induce faults manually. Finally the fault distance can be determined.

Index Terms- Arduino UNO, Underground Fault, Resistance, LCD

1. INTRODUCTION

A bundle of electrical conductors used for carrying electricity is called as a cable. An underground cable generally has one or more conductors covered with suitable insulation and a protective cover [1]. Commonly used materials for insulation are varnished cambric or impregnated paper. Fault in a cable can be any defect or non-homogeneity that diverts the path of current or affects the performance of the cable. So it is necessary to correct the fault.

Power Transmission can be done in both overhead as well as in underground cables. But unlike underground cables the overhead cables have the drawback of being easily prone to the effects of rainfall, snow, thunder, lightning etc. This requires cables with reliability, increased safety, ruggedness and greater service. So underground cables are

preferred in many areas specially in urban places. , When it is easy to detect and correct the faults in overhead line by mere observation, it is not possible to do so in an underground cable. As they are buried deep in the soil it is not easy to detect the abnormalities in them. Even when a fault is found to be present it is very difficult to detect the exact location of the fault. This leads to digging of the entire area to detect and correct the fault which in turn causes wastage of money and manpower. So it is necessary to know the exact location of faults in the underground cables.

Whatever the fault is, the voltage of the cable has the tendency to change abruptly whenever a fault occurs [2]. We make use of this voltage change across the series resistors to detect the fault.

2. FAULTS IN UNDERGROUND CABLES

2.1 OPEN CIRCUIT FAULTS

These faults occur due to the failure of one or more conductors. The most common causes of these faults include joint failures of cables and overhead lines, and failure of one or more phase of circuit breaker and also due to melting of a fuse or conductor in one or more phases .Open circuit faults are also called as series faults. These are unsymmetrical or unbalanced type of faults except three phase open fault.

2.2 SHORT CIRCUIT FAULTS

A short circuit can be defined as an abnormal connection of very low impedance between two points of different potential, whether made intentionally or accidentally. These are the most common and severe kind of faults, resulting in the flow of abnormal high currents through the equipment or transmission lines. If these faults are allowed to persist even for a short period, it leads to